

Cadmium accumulation on shallot which planted on cadmium contaminated land

*Cicik Oktasari Handayani, Triyani Dewi, and Ina Zulaehah
Indonesian Agricultural Environment Research Institute,
Jalan Raya Jakenan-Jaken Km 5 Pati, Central Java, Indonesia
Corresponding author :cicik.oktasari@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Agricultural land contaminated with heavy metals is a serious problem due to its toxic effects and accumulation through the food chain which decrease land quality and disrupt human health. Cadmium (Cd) is one of the heavy metals that are harmful to human health. This research was conducted to determine cadmium accumulation in onion plants grown on Cd contaminated land. This research was carried out in the shallow field in Igirklanceng Village, Sirampog District, Brebes Regency in 2017. Experiments used a Randomized Block Design (RBD), with 3 replications and eight treatments. The results showed that Cd concentration is accumulated in the tubers < stem < roots. The average concentration of Cd in tubers grown on contaminated soil ranges from 1.46 to 2.00 mg/kg. This means that the concentration of Cd in the tubers is higher than the maximum limit allowed to be consumed according to BPOM (2017) which is equal to 0.05 mg/kg so that efforts need to be made to reduce the Cd concentration in the soil intensively until the Cd content in the soil is lower than the maximum limit.

Keywords: *accumulation, cadmium, shallot*

INTRODUCTION

Cadmium (Cd) is a heavy metal that is carcinogenic and toxic or toxic even in low concentrations (Khan et al., 2015a). Contamination by toxic metals in agricultural land can cause stress on plants three times greater than that of pesticides (Jeliazko, 2001). Cadmium is spread in the environment through among other things, various human activities such as waste disposal, phosphate fertilizer, industrial activities and human settlements (Wagner, 1993).

Heavy metals in agricultural land can be absorbed by plants and accumulated in the roots, leaves, fruits and seeds (Fang and Zhu, 2014).

Cadmium accumulation (Cd) in plants can inhibit nutrient uptake (Pardo et al., 2013), inhibit photosynthetic distribution (Xue et al., 2013; Xue et al., 2014), inhibit photosynthetic rate, enzyme activity, increasing peroxide compounds and causing genetic changes (Dezar et al., 2005).

Cd accumulation in various types of plants has been widely studied and shows a variety of responses. Greger and Lofstedt (2004) examined the uptake and distribution of Cd in roots, leaves and seeds in various wheat cultivars. The results of Sekara et al. (2005) showed that red beet plants were able to accumulate large amounts of Cd in the leaves, while its accumulation in the roots is 2.8 times smaller than in the leaves. In pumpkin plants (pumpkin), the largest Cd is accumulated in the leaves, at least in the stem and fruit. The Cd accumulation in barley roots is 4 times greater than the panicle, and 7 times greater than that found in the seeds. The results of this study concluded that red beet, pumpkin, chycory, common bean, white cabbage and parsnip plants accumulated the largest Cd in their leaf organs. Wang et al. (2007) studied 2 corn cultivars (Nongda No.108 and Liyu No.6), the uptake and concentration of Cd in the roots and shoots of both corn cultivars were different, but both cultivars accumulated greater Cd in the roots than the shoots. Romkens et al. (2009) examined the uptake and distribution of Cd from 12 rice varieties. Sharma et al. (2010) found that the accumulation of Cd in the root of *Pisum sativum* was greater than the shoot portion. The content of Cd in the part of green mustard root, chicory and kailan is greater than shoots (Susana et al., 2013).

A high Cd concentration can reduce content of Ca, Mg, and K in tomato tissue (Khan et al., 2016) and cucumber (Burzynski, 1988). Bioaccumulation of Cd causes changes in various physiological functions by influencing N metabolism (Chaffei et al., 2004). Being an important part of genetic, structural and metabolic components, N plays an important role in plant growth and metabolism (Hasan et al., 2008).

The absorption of Cd by vegetables from the soil is the main exposure pathway for humans (Franz et al., 2008; Kobayashi et al., 2008), and exposure through vegetable consumption to about 70-80% of total intake in humans (Olsson et al., 2002; Yang et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2016). Cd has an adverse effect on the health of the human body where bones and kidneys are the most important target organs (Aitio and Tritscher, 2004).

Consumption of food crops contaminated with heavy metals causes accumulation of heavy metals in the organs of the body that cause various diseases and disorders of bodily functions such as fractures, cancer, damage to the heart, liver, kidneys, lungs, and mutagenesis that can cause death (Friberg et al., 1992; Portier 2012).

Cadmium pollution on agricultural land in several regions in Indonesia has exceeded the permissible threshold, so it needs to get serious attention by industry players, farmers, and the government. Cadmium contamination can be prevented through good management of industrial waste, reducing excessive input of inorganic fertilizers and pesticides, minimizing soil treatment, water management, planting heavy metal absorbing grass, and strict supervision from the government. Methods of controlling contaminated land can be carried out according to the level of contamination.

This research was conducted to determine cadmium accumulation in onion plants grown on contaminated soil Cd.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was carried out in the shallot farmer land in Igirklandeng Village, Sirampog Subdistrict, Brebes Regency, Central Java Province, which had a high grade of Cd in 2017. Experiments used a randomized block design (RBD), with 3 replications, and eight treatments as follows:

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|--|
| T0 : control | T5 : biochar + biological fertilizer |
| T1 : compost | T6 : compost + biological fertilizer |
| T2 : biochart | T7 : biochar + compost + biological fertilizer |
| T3 : biochar + compost (biocompost) | T8 : treatment of farmers |
| T4 : biological fertilizer | |

The shallot seeds of Bima Curut varieties were planted in each plot. The size of the plot adjusts to the farmer plot. Biofertilizers, compost, biochar, and biocompost were applied before planting. Compost, biochar, and biocompost were used as much as 2 t/ha (according to the dose used by farmers) which applied before planting during tillage. Biocompost was a mixture of biochar : compost (1: 4 w/w). All of these treatments were applied during tillage, then the soil is left for 1 week.

Inorganic fertilizers of N, P, and K used were 200 kg N/ha, 90 kg P₂O₅/ha, and 150 kg K₂O/ha. As a source of N, P, and K used were urea, SP-36, and KCl, respectively. P fertilizer is given at once before planting. N and K fertilizers are given twice at the age of 15 and 30 days after planting (DAP), each

half dose by sowing on each plot of onion plants. Seedlings were planted with a spacing of 15 cm x 20 cm.

The parameters observed were Cd content in the initial soil after ameliorant application and Cd concentration in plants (onion leaves and tubers). Analysis of Cd content on soil and plants was done at the Laboratory of Agricultural Environmental Research Institute.

Parameters of Cd heavy metal data in soil and plants were carried out in quantitative descriptive analysis. All parameters are analyzed using the Microsoft Excel and SAS Window Release 9.00 program tools.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The availability of heavy metals in the soil is naturally influenced by several factors including: soil pH, soil organic matter content, CEC, and soil type (Sing and Steinnes, 1994). Addition of organic matter can source from organic fertilizer. The use of phosphorus fertilizer is generally considered as one of the main sources of Cd input for agricultural soils (Smolder and Mertens, 2013).

The availability of Cd heavy metal in the soil can be seen in Figure 1. The available metal content of Cd in treatment of biochar + biological fertilizer is the highest as much as 0.441 mg/kg. While the lowest of Cd availability is treatment of biological fertilizer.

Figure 1. Cd concentration in soil on different treatments

Shallot plant growth can be referred with parameters of plant height and number of leaves. The height of shallots up to 70 days after planting (DAP) is still increasing as shown in Figure 2. The number of leaves up to 70 days after planting is still visible (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Shallot plant height in several treatments

Note :

T0 : control

T1 : compost

T2 : biochart

T3 : biochar + compost (biocompost)

T4 : biological fertilizer

T5 : biochar + biological fertilizer

T6 : compost + biological fertilizer

T7 : biochar + compost + biological fertilizer

T8 : treatment of farmers

Figure 3. Number of onion plant leaves

Cd metal has a significant negative impact on the nutritional value of plants and growth rate in most plants grown in contaminated soil Cd. The significant negative impact affects nutrient deficiency in plants (Khan et al., 2015b). As shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3 in the T5 treatment, it grows delayed with most other plants. The greatest possibility of this is caused by the highest presence of available Cd concentration in soil than other treatments.

Heavy metals enter plant cells through the same transportation as the system used to absorb the macro and micronutrient elements needed by plants. So it is necessary to make efforts to maintain the condition of agricultural land so that the heavy metal content in it does not exceed the critical limit that has been determined.

The concentration of Cd metal in the roots, stems and onion bulbs can be seen in Table 1. The average concentration of Cd metal in the roots, stems and onion bulbs is 2.16-2.93 mg/kg; 2.12-2.44 mg/kg; 1.46-2.00 mg/kg, respectively. The highest accumulation of Cd Cd is in the root but the lowest is in the tuber.

Table 1. The content of Cd heavy metals in shallots

Treatment	Total Cd (mg/kg)		
	Root	Stem	Tuber
T0 : Control	2.23a	2.12a	1.71a
T1 : Compost	2.86a	2.19a	1.81a
T2 : Biochar	2.43a	2.44a	1.63a
T3 : Bio compost	2.36a	2.29a	2,00a
T4 : Biological fertilizer	2.93a	2.38a	1.65a
T5 : Biochar + biological fertilizer	2.16a	2.18a	1.70a
T6 : Compost + biological fertilizer	2.40a	2.34a	1.60a
T7 : Biocompost + biological fertilizer	2.55a	2.64a	1.46a
T8 : Treatment of farmers	2.38a	2.57a	1.59a

Note: The values followed by the same letters are not significantly different at $P < 0.05$ by DMRT. Lowercase letters are read vertically (columns) and capital letters read horizontally (rows).

The concentration of Cd metal in roots can cause nutrients deficiency by competing for nutrient absorption which have similar chemical properties such as Ca and Mg (Barcelo and Poschenrieder, 1990). A high Cd concentration can cause reduction Ca, Mg, and K in tomato tissue (Khan et al., 2016) and cucumber (Burzynski, 1988). Bioaccumulation of Cd causes changes in various physiological functions by influencing N metabolism (Chaffei et al., 2004). The N element N is an important part of genetics because it plays an important role in the growth and metabolism of plants.

The average value of metal Cd accumulation in shallot tubers is 1.46-2.00 mg/kg. This concentration is higher than the maximum limit that is allowed to be consumed according to BPOM (2017) that is equal to 0.05 mg/kg. Cd metal will be gradually accumulated in the human body and eventually cause a variety of adverse health effects especially causing bone damage and nephron toxicity (Nordberg et al., 1991; WHO, 1992).

CONCLUSIONS

1. The shallot absorbs Cd from soil and be accumulated in the tubers < stems < roots.
2. The Cd concentration in tubers is 1.46-2.00 mg/kg which is higher than the maximum allowed for consumption according to BPOM (2017) which is 0.05 mg/kg.
3. There needs to be further research to intensify the concentration of Cd in the soil intensively until the Cd content in the soil is below the prescribed maximum limit

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was conducted using national budget of the Agricultural Environment Research Institute in 2017. We thank all the researchers and technicians of the EP3 Division.

REFERENCE

- Aitio, A., and A. Tritscher. 2004. Effects on health of cadmium-WHO approaches and conclusions. *Biometals.*, **17**(5):491.
- Barcelo and Poschenrieder, 1990. Plant water relations as affected by heavy metal stress: a review. *J. Plant Nut.*, **13**:1-37.
- BPOM. 2017. Batas maksimum cemaran logam berat dalam pangan olahan. Peraturan Kepala Badan Pengawas Obat dan Makanan RI, No.23.
- Burzynski, M. 1988. The uptake and accumulation of phosphorus and nitrates and the activity of nitrate reductase in cucumber seedlings treated with Pb and Cd. *Acta Soc. Bot. Pol.*, **57**:349-359.
- Chaffei, C., K. Pageau, A. Suzuki, H. Gouia, M.H. Ghorbel, and C. Masclaux-Daubresse. 2004. Cadmium toxicity induced changes in nitrogen management in *Lycopersicon esculentum* leading to a metabolic safeguard through an amino acid storage strategy. *Plant Cell Physiol.*, **45**(11):1681-1693.
- Dezar, Fedrigo, and Chan. 2005. The promoter of the sunflower HD-Zip protein gene Hahb4 directs tissue specific expression and is inducible by water stress, high salt concentrations and ABA. *Plant Sci.*, **169**:447-456
- Fang, B., and X. Zhu. 2014. High content of five heavy metals in four fruits: Evidence from a case study of Pujiang County, Zhejiang Province, China. *Food Control.*, **39**:62-67.
- Franz, E., P. Romkens, L. van Raamsdonk, and I. van Der Fels-Klerx. 2008. A chain modeling approach to estimate the impact of soil cadmium pollution on human dietary exposure. *J. Food Prot.*, **71**:2504-2513.
- Friberg, L., C.G. Elinder, and T. Kjellstroem. 1992. Cadmium. Geneva, the United Nations Environment Programme, the Internat. Labour Organisation, the World Health Organization. Geneva. 280 p.

- Greger, M., and M. Lofstedt. 2004. Comparison of uptake and distribution of cadmium indifferent cultivars of Bread and Durum Wheat. *Crop Science.*, **44**(2):501-507.
- Hasan, S.A., S. Hayat, B. Ali, and A. Ahmad. 2008. 28-Homobrassinolide protects chickpea (*Cicer arietinum*) from cadmium toxicity by stimulating antioxidants. *Environ. Pollut.*, **151**(1):60-66.
- Jeliazko, V.D. 2001. Study on heavy metals absorption by plants. Doctoral dissertations available from proquest. University of Massachusetts Amherst. <http://www.lib.unicorn/disesertation/fulcit>. (accessed 27 Juni 2007).
- Khan, A., S. Khan, M.A. Khan, Z. Qamar, and M. Waqas. 2015a. The uptake and bioaccumulation of heavy metals by food plants, their effects on plants nutrients, and associated health risk: a review. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.*, **22**(18):13772-13799.
- Khan, S., M. Waqas, F. Fenghua Ding, I. Shamshad, H.P.H. Arp, and G. Li. 2015b. The influence of various biochars on the bioaccessibility and bioaccumulation of PAHs and potentially toxic elements to turnips (*Brassica rapa* L.). *J. Hazard. Mater.*, **300**:243-253.
- Khan, A., S. Khan, M. Alam, M.A. Khan, M. Aamir, Z. Qamar, Z.U. Rehman, and S. Perveen. 2016. Toxic metal interactions affect the bioaccumulation and dietary intake of macro-and micro-nutrients. *Chemosphere.*, **146**:121-128.
- Kobayashi, E., Y. Suwazono, M. Dochi, R. Honda, M. Nishijo, and T. Kido. 2008. Estimation of benchmark doses as threshold levels of urinary cadmium based on excretion of β 2-microglobulin in cadmium polluted and non-polluted regions in Japan. *Toxicol. Lett.*, **179**:108-112.
- Nordberg, M., T. Jin, and G.F. Nordberg. 1991. Cadmium, metallothionein and renal tubular toxicity. *IARC Sci. Publ.*, **118**: 293-297.
- Olsson, I.M., I. Bensryd, T. Lundh, H. Ottosson, S. Skerfving, and A. Oskarsson. 2002. Cadmium in vassociation of renal effects. *Environ. Health Perspect.*, **110**:1185-1190.
- Pardo, B.S., R.O. Carpena, R. Carpena, and P. Zornoza. 2013. Cadmium in white lupin nodules: Impact on nitrogen and carbon metabolism. *J. Plant Physiol.*, **170**:265-271.
- Portier, C.J. 2012. Toxicological Profile for Cadmium. Public Health Service Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry. Georgia. 487 p.

- Susana, Rini., and D. Suswati. 2013. Bioakumulasi dan distribusi Cd pada akar dan pucuk 3 jenis tanaman family brassicaceae : implementasinya untuk fitoremediasi. *Jurnal Manusia dan Lingkungan.*, **20**(2):221-228.
- Romkens, P.F.A.M., F.Y. Guo, C.L. Chu, T.S. Liu, C.F. Chiang, and G.F. Koopmans. 2009. Prediction of cadmium uptake by brown rice and derivation of soil-plant transfer models to improve. Soil protection guidelines, *Journal Environmental Pollution.*, **I57** :2435-2444.
- Sekara, A., M. Poniedzialek, J. Ciura, and E. Jedrzczyk. 2005. Cadmium and lead accumulation and distribution in theorgan of nine crops: implications for phytoremediation. *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies.*, **14**(4):509-516.
- Sharma S., P. Sharma, and Mehrotra. 2010. Bioaccumulation of heavy metals in *Pisum sativum* L. growing in fly ash amanded soil. *Journal of American Science.*, **16**(6):43-50.
- Sing, B.R., and E. Steinnes. 1994. Soil and water contamination by heavy metals. In: Lal, R. And A. Stewart (Eds.). *Soil Process and Water Quality. Advances in Soil Science.*. Boca Raton, Florida: Lewis Publisher. pp. 233-271.
- Smolders, E., and J. Mertens. 2013. Cadmium. In: Alloway, B.J. (Ed.). *Heavy Metals in SoilsNetherlands* . *Springer.*, **22**:283–311.
- Wagner, H. 1993 *Pharmazeutische biologie*, 5, Aufl. Gustav-Fischer Verlag. P.103, Berlin, Heidelberg, New York, USA.
- Wang, M., J. Zou, X. Duan, W. Jiang, and D. Liu. 2007. Cadmium accumulation and itseffect on metal uptake in maize (*Zea mays* L). *Journal Bioresource Technology.*, **98**:82-88.
- Wang, M., W. Chen, and C. Peng. 2016. Risk assessment of Cd polluted paddy soils in the industrial and township areas in Hunan, Southern China. *Chemosphere.*, **144**:346-351.
- WHO. 1992. Cd. *Environmental Health Criteria*. vol. 134. World Health Organization (WHO), Geneva.
- Xue, Z., H. Gao, and S. Zhao. 2014. Effects of cadmium on the photosynthetic activity in mature and young leaves of soybean plants. *Environ. Sci.and Pollution Res.*, **21**(6):4656-4664.
- Xue, Z.C., H.Y. Gao, and L.T. Zhang. 2013. Effects of cadmium on growth, photosynthetic rate and chlorophyll content in leaves of soybean seedlings. *Biologia Plantarum.*, **57**(3):587-590.

Yang, Y., W. Chen, M. Wang, Y. Li, and C. Peng, C., 2017. Evaluating the potential health risk of toxic trace elements in vegetables: accounting for variations in soil factors. *Sci. Total Environ.*, **584**:942-949.